

Investigation of antibiotic resistance and classification of antibiotic

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Abstract

This is a review article based on the research paper based on “The Role of Antibiotics in Nature” and “Antimicrobial drug development”. Antibiotics are used to treat infections caused by bacteria. Antibiotics fight the bacteria by either killing them or making it difficult for the bacteria to grow or multiply inside the host body. Based on the ability of the antibiotic to kill or arrest growth of the bacteria, they can be classified as bactericidal and bacteriostatic. Antibiotics can be also classified based on their mechanism of action. As the use of antibiotics started to increase certain bacteria became resistant to antibiotics. Resistant infectious bacteria are becoming more difficult to treat with any available antibiotics. This write-up introduces the antibiotic discovery and how over time the resistance towards antibiotics has started to build up allowing bacteria to grow and multiply inside the host body. This resistance may even cause infection to spread to other people making it a global threat.

Keywords: Classification, resistance, bactericidal, bacteriostatic

1. Introduction

Infections caused by bacteria can result in serious illnesses and even death. Antibiotics play a very important role in treating infections. They can effectively kill the germ in the human body. Antibiotics are used commonly and can be prescribed by our doctors. Antibiotics help to fight infection in humans or animals by killing the bacteria or making it difficult for bacteria to multiply in the host's body.

But are all bacteria harmful? Not at all. Some harmless bacteria are already present inside our body, and they are called commensals. They play a significant role in helping our body by competing with or killing harmful bacteria. Antibiotics are commonly used in this inter-bacterial warfare. Antibiotics can also be produced by soil bacteria or fungi which helps them to compete for food and water and any other limited resources for survival which makes the microbes an advantage as antibiotics help them to kill their competition. Once discovered, we now use this same tool to kill harmful bacteria. Despite all the benefits of an antibiotic that fights against bacteria, it may sometimes lead to antibiotic resistance due to the overuse of antibiotics. For instance, as the medicinal use of penicillin increased, bacteria started to become resistant to the antibiotic. While natural processes can result in resistance to antibiotics too, high human usage accelerates the process of resistance evolution.

2. How Antibiotics were first discovered

Alexander Flemings first started to experiment on the colonies of *Staphylococcus* which are bacteria responsible for causing boils, sore throats etc. He began to spectate Petri dishes containing *Staphylococcus* bacteria when suddenly he noticed something unusual. One of the Petri dishes was dotted with colonies where some blob of mold was growing. It looked like something inhibited bacterial growth as the zone around the mold found a rare strain of *Penicillium notatum* clear. This

“mold juice” could kill harmful bacteria, including *streptococcus*, *meningococcus*, and many more. The provided sample came out to be very unstable thus he was only able to work on crude material and prepare solutions. Afterward, Flemings published his research in the British Journal of experimental pathology in June 1929. He introduced his research (discovery of penicillin) as only potentially therapeutic. Later this research was taken forward at Oxford university in 1939 when some scientists began to work on the purification and chemistry of penicillin.

Albert Alexandra became the first recipient of penicillin. In his case, the wound was affected due to scratching the side of his mouth while pruning roses which lead to significant symptoms in various parts of the human body that could have resulted in life-threatening infections. He was treated with antibiotics and after some time looking at his speedy recovery many industries were interested to invest in this medical advancement. Many of them started to conduct research in the field and tried to improve the yield of antibiotics as well as produce it commercially.

3. How Antibiotics work

Different classes of antibiotics carry out different processes in the bacterial cell which inhibit the growth of bacterial cells in the host's body. All the classes of antibiotics “target” certain components in the cell. Some antibiotics, when they are first introduced to bacteria, attack the cell wall. These antibiotics stop the synthesis of a molecule called peptidoglycan. This molecule helps build the cell wall of the bacteria. Thus, when antibiotics attack this particular molecule in bacteria it stops the spread of infection in the human body.

In other cases, a class of antibiotics called quinolones prevents DNA replication in bacteria by targeting DNA gyrase (an enzyme that helps in the unwinding of DNA in the replication process).

Thus, this results in antibiotics preventing bacteria from multiplying and spreading the infection any further.

Other classes of antibiotics sometimes attack ribosomes which carry out the process of protein synthesis. In this, the drug prevents key molecules from binding to ribosomes, thus arresting protein production. If proteins are not produced in bacteria necessary functions may not be carried out resulting in inefficiency and death of bacterial cells. On the other hand, some antibiotics might inhibit RNA synthesis (a process where DNA is transcribed into RNA) which does not let protein production in bacterial cells.

To understand how different antibiotics work we can look closely at Chloramphenicol as an example. This antibiotic was discovered in 1948 and was first used in treating serious bacterial infections but now the use of this antibiotic is close to negligible and is only used in the case of a life-threatening infection. Chloramphenicol diffuses through the bacteria cell wall and binds with the 50s ribosome subunit; this hampers the process of peptidyl transferase activity. As the peptidyl transferase activity is hampered the transfer of amino acid is also stopped which prevents the formation of peptide chains and blocks the peptide bonds. This will stop the process of protein synthesis preventing cell multiplication or delaying the process of cell multiplication of bacterial cells.

Antibiotics are divided into classes, for example, all quinolones have a common structure and mechanism of action. But even within the same class of drugs, there are certain modifications made to each molecule which slightly modifies their action.

This results in each family of drugs targeting specific microbes which have slightly different profiles from each other and work differently on every bacteria. Whereas the “generation” of antibiotics denotes its chemical structure which can be changed to improve the action of the antibiotic on the bacteria accordingly.

4. Antibiotics Classification

Antibiotics are classified into two classes according to their mechanism which include bactericidal and bacteriostatic. Where bactericidal antibiotics kill bacteria (for example, by inhibiting cell wall synthesis), bacteriostatic antibiotics inhibit bacteria’s growth and reproduction (for example, by interfering with bacterial cellular metabolism).

4.1 Beta-lactams

Beta-lactam is an antibiotic that contains a beta-lactam ring in its chemical structure. These antibiotics have a favorable ratio of therapeutic to toxic effect and some of the new agents in the same class have shown some incredible enhancement in antibacterial spectrums. This class of antibiotics targets the synthesis of the cell walls and interrupts the transpeptidation process which helps in building the cell wall by linking the peptidoglycan component in the bacterial cell. They attack specific targets which help in the synthesis of cell walls such as PBPs known as penicillin-binding proteins. It helps polymerization and modification of peptidoglycan which is the stress-bearing element of the bacterial cell walls.

These enzymes include transpeptidases, carboxypeptidases, and endopeptidases which are found in an inactive state on the inner surface of the bacterial cell membrane. These enzymes are involved during the growth and division of the cell wall which takes place in reshaping the cell wall. Thus inactivation of PBP eventually leads to cell death, whereas some of the PBPs are important for the development of cell wall such as PBP 1A, 1B, 2, and 3 but some of the PBPs which includes PBP 4, 5 and 6 are not essential for the development of bacterial cell wall. Some of the examples are penicillin, cephalosporins, monobactams, and carbapenems.

4.2 Aminoglycoside

Aminoglycoside is a class of antibiotics that consists of various agents. The aminoacyl site of 16s ribosomal RNA within the 30s subunit is the target site of aminoglycosides and leads to the misreading of the genetic code and inhibition of translocation. Examples of aminoglycosides are streptomycin, gentamicin, and neomycin and they work against many bacteria.

4.3 Gyrase inhibitor

Gyrase enzyme is used in DNA replication or gene expression to look after the unwinding and winding of the DNA. As DNA is found in a very wound state tightly packed inside the nucleus and only opens up during the replication and gene expression process. When this inhibitor acts on the DNA it interferes with the DNA cleavage function of the enzyme. DNA damage affects the stabilization of the covalent gyrase DNA complex which causes the formation of reactive oxygen species resulting in cell death. Quinolones and aminocoumarins are two families of antibiotics that have demonstrated in clinical studies that DNA gyrase is a workable target. The two subunits of DNA gyrase consist of GyrA and GyrB which is a member of the type two family of topoisomerases that controls the topological state of DNA. Aminocoumarin antibiotic inhibits the DNA gyrase by competing with the ATP which binds with the GYrB subunit and blocks the ATP hydrolysis function of the enzyme.

4.4 Folate inhibitor

Synthesis of folic helps in the transfer of single carbon units among different compounds which also includes nucleotide synthesis. It is an essential nutrient for protein and nucleic acid synthesis. Folic acid is synthesized by bacteria which includes para-amino benzoic acid as a substrate. The growth of the cell requires folic acid. Where some food can diffuse through the cell, but folic acid cannot cross cell walls through diffusion. To transport folic acid thus it needs to synthesize folic acid from PABA. Folate synthesis is inhibited at two different sites by sulfonamides and trimethoprim. As sulfonamides are like PABA structurally, PABA helps in the transportation of important materials across the membrane. On the other hand, trimethoprim inhibits the enzyme dihydrofolate reductase, which prevents dihydrofolate from being converted to tetrahydrofolate.

Table1: Classification of antibiotics

Function	Antibiotics	Bactericidal or bacteriostatic	Mode of action	Structure	Reference
	Chloramphenicol	Bacteriostatic	Prevents cell growth by inhibiting protein synthesis		https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chloramphenicol
	Oxazolidinones	Bacteriostatic	Inhibit the bacteria from protein synthesis which thus leads to cell death		https://www.wikiwand.com/en/2-Oxazolidone
	Sulfonamides	Bacteriostatic	It does not kill the bacteria cell but inhibits its cell growth and multiplication		https://study.com/academy/lesson/sulfonamide-chemical-structure-derivatives.html

Commonly act as a bacteriostatic agent (Restricting growth and reproduction)	Tetracyclines	Bacteriostatic	Inhibit protein synthesis by preventing bacteria's cell growth		https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tetracycline
	Macrolides	Bacteriostatic	Inhibit the bacteria from protein synthesis which thus leads to cell death		https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Macrolide
Commonly act as bactericidal agents (Causing bacterial cell death)	B-Lactams	Bactericidal	Inhibit bacteria's cell wall biosynthesis		https://www.khanacademy.org/test-prep/mcat/physical-sciences-practice/physical-sciences-practice-tut/e/the-chemical-structure-consequences-of-beta-lactams
	Aminoglycosides	Bactericidal	Inhibits the bacteria from protein synthesis which thus leads to cell death		https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aminoglycoside
	Glycopeptides	Bactericidal	Inhibits bacteria's cell wall biosynthesis		https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Glycopeptide_antibiotic
	Quinolones	Bactericidal	Interferes with bacteria DNA replication and transcription in bacteria cell		https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quinolone_antibiotic
	Ansamycins	Bactericidal	Inhibits RNA synthesis which leads to cell death		https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ansamycin

	Streptogramins	Bactericidal	Inhibits the bacteria from protein synthesis which thus leads to cell death		https://quod.lib.umich.edu/cgi/i/image/image-idx?rgn1=ic_all;op2=And;rgn2=ic_all;op3=And;rgn3=ic_all;ic=medchem;ic.med=1;q1=quinupristin;back=ba;ck1164516011;size=20;subview=detail;resnum=1;view=entry;lastview=thumbnail;cc=medchem;ic.entryid=x.865;viewid=QUINUPRISTIN.TIF
	Lipopeptides	Bactericidal	It disrupts multiple cell membrane function which leads to cell death		https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/article.html/2015/ce/c5ce01335a

5. How does antibiotic resistance occur

Antibiotic resistance is said to have evolved when the antibiotic is unable to kill or arrest the growth of bacteria. When bacteria become resistant to a specific antibiotic it becomes difficult to treat the infection. Resistance mechanisms are a type of protection that bacteria might evolve against antibiotics. Specific proteins are made through the DNA of the germs which will determine the germ's resistance mechanism. The resistance mechanisms are of different kinds as illustrated below.

5.1 Restrict access to the antibiotic

By changing the entryways or limiting the possible number of entryways the germs can restrict access. An example is gram-negative bacteria which have an outer membrane that helps in keeping certain unwanted particles away from the bacteria. The outer membrane helps to protect the

bacteria in certain environments too. Similarly, when antibiotics approach this bacteria it restricts the antibiotic from entering the cells hence attaining antibiotic resistance

5.2 Get rid of the antibiotic or antifungal

Using pumps built into their cell walls, bacteria eliminate antibiotic that tries to enter the cell. For example, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacteria produce certain pumps to get rid of any antibiotic drugs which enter the bacteria cell.

5.3 Change or destroy the antibiotic

Through enzymes, germs change or destroy the antibiotic, and proteins help to break down the drug. Bacteria's such as *Klebsiella pneumonia* produces enzymes called carbapenemases which help to break down carbapenem drugs and other lactam drugs.

5.4 Change the targets for the antibiotic and antifungal

Some antibiotics mechanism includes specific designs and specific parts to destroy the bacteria cell. Here the germs tend to change the antibiotics target by changing the change so that the drug no longer fits. Some bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* have the MCR-1 gene which can ass a compound to the outside so that the drug colistin cannot latch onto it.

5.5 Bypass the effects of the antibiotic

Through developing new cell processes germs can avoid the antibiotic's target and this is done by some *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria which can then bypass the drug effects of trimethoprim.

6. How does Antibiotic resistance spread

Antibiotics can enter the bodies of animals when they are treated with antibiotics hence, they can carry resistant bacteria. Even vegetables can be contaminated with antibiotic-resistant bacteria from animal manure used as fertilizer. Through food and direct contact with animals, antibiotic-resistant bacteria can spread to humans. Antibiotic-resistant bacteria can also spread from the treated patient as bacteria develop resistance to antibiotics as a natural, adaptive reaction. Antibiotic resistance can be spread through human contact such as when humans receive antibiotics in the hospital and then carry antibiotic-resistant bacteria. This can be spread to other patients through unclean or contaminated objects.

Conclusion

Antibiotic resistance results in a massive setback as it leads to higher medical costs, delayed hospital stays, and increased mortality. The world is in urgent need of a solution to antibiotic resistance as it remains a major threat. It is rising to dangerously high levels in all parts. The list of potentially untreatable diseases is ever-expanding including pneumonia, tuberculosis, blood poisoning, and foodborne diseases, these diseases are becoming harder to treat. To reduce the threat of increasing antibiotic resistance WHO has issued many guidelines which suggest that antibiotics should only be used when prescribed by a health professional, prevent infection by taking precautions, and sustain a hygienic lifestyle.

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